

Short communication

***Mokrzeckia obscura* (Hym.: Pteromalidae), a hyperparasitoid of diamondback moth and a new record from Iran**

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چکیده

در بررسی‌های مربوط به شناسایی پارازیتوئیدهای مراحل نابالغ بید کلم، (*Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lep.: Plutellidae) در مزارع کلم و کلم گل استان اصفهان، یک گونه پارازیتوئید ثانویه به نام *Mokrzeckia obscura* Graham از خانواده‌ی Pteromalidae جمع‌آوری و شناسایی شد که برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود. این گونه از پرورش لاروهای بید کلم که توسط پارازیته شده بودند، به دست آمد. *Cotesia plutellae* (Kurdjumov) (Hym.: Braconidae)

A hyperparasitoid was identified in a field study on larval and pupal parasitoids of diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lep.: Plutellidae), in Isfahan province during May to October 2009. *Mokrzeckia obscura* Graham, 1969 (Hym.: Pteromalidae) was reared from an endoparasitoid, *Cotesia plutellae* (Kurdjumov) (Hym., Braconidae), which was obtained from *P. xylostella* larvae collected from Mobarakeh county. This is the first record of *M. obscura* from Iran. This species belongs to the subfamily Pteromalinae and has already been reported from the UK (Noyes, 2010).

Diagnosis – Female. Body length 2.6 mm; head and thorax bluish green; gaster bronze-green, basal tergite blue-green, the remaining tergites extensively suffused with purplish; antennae fuscous, proximal half of scape testaceous; coxa concolorous with thorax, femora fuscous, rest of leg testaceous, tarsi brown apically; wing hyaline, veins brown (Graham, 1969).

The hyperparasitoid was identified by the third author.

References

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